

Multiparty Session Types: Separation and Encodability Results

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The talk first introduces the history and background of types for communications and multiparty session types, relating to the history of Computer Science in Oxford.

Multiparty session types (MPST) are a type discipline for enforcing the structured, deadlock-free communication of concurrent and message-passing programs. Traditional MPST have a limited form of choice in which alternative communication possibilities are offered by a single participant and selected by another.

Mixed choice multiparty session types (MCMP) extend the choice construct to include both selections and offers in the same choice. This talk presents a mixed choice synchronous multiparty session calculus and its typing system, which guarantees communication safety and deadlock-freedom.

We then discuss the expressiveness of nine subcalculi of the MCMP-calculus by examining:

- Encodability: whether a good encoding exists from one calculus to another.
- Separation: whether no good encoding exists from one calculus to another.

The highlight is that binary (2-party) mixed sessions by Casal et al. (2022) are strictly less expressive than the MCMP-calculus.

Joint work with Kirstin Peters, appeared in LICS'24: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.08104>